

Optimization of a Deflection-based Rappel Device

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ABSTRACT

Performance and ease of use of rappel devices is an important issue for outdoor enthusiasts, military personnel, and rope rescue. Current methods for determining performance are largely experimental. This paper presents an approach to a numerical optimization of rappel device configurations and the results obtained, as well as recommendations for expanding the analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

In some instances it would be beneficial to rappel multiple people down the same rope at the same time. One case would be fast roping in the military where multiple soldiers need to descend quickly from a helicopter. In most cases having multiple people on a single rope can be dangerous or impossible. For multiple people to be on the same rope the equipment being used must help prevent anyone from falling onto the the next person below and continue to work regardless of the tension in the rope. Such a device would need to be reliable for multiple uses.

Designing a device that can meet all three of these requirements is difficult and has made many improvements through trial and error. Early on climbing devices were limited and many people would tie themselves off if using a rope. It wasn't until the early 1900's that equipment began developing rapidly to the point where rappelling became commonly done safely [4]. As technology has improved, new climbing gear has been created and sold. However, some climbing gear works much better than others. Many improvements can be made to the design process to explore rappelling designs that would allow multiple people to descend the same rope.

One way to improve the design process is through optimization of the device shape. In this report we present one way to optimize a device made of links by changing its configuration. The design objective is to minimize the pretension needed to support 400 lbs of dead weight. Future research would be to modify the static design so that the

user may actively adjust the weight supported by the rope for a wide range of pretensions. In this report we will discuss how our approach influenced our decisions, what challenges we encountered, and what design was optimal.

1.1 Background

Rappel and belay devices have existed for many years, and there is a large industry that has produced a wide variety of devices with different advantages depending on the intended application. Many efforts have been made to quantify and make comparisons of the relative effectiveness of existing devices in an attempt to aid those exploring the many possibilities. Stronge et al talk about an "amplification factor" for belay devices, which is caused by friction and bending of the rope. This allows a belayer to hold a force of several kN with a much smaller hand force [3].

The sources mentioned here as well as many others have presented significant experimental results allowing us to characterize and understand the effectiveness of many existing belay and rappel devices. However, we found little evidence of the use of analytical methods for designing a device to perform as desired. According to Manin et al, climber and manufacturer experience are the basis for the development of new designs [2]. A formal attempt to numerically find an optimal configuration for a rappel device seems to be a needed contribution to the field.

2. METHODS

2.1 Analysis

We began by developing a mathematical model of the device that would allow us to calculate the tension it creates in the rope. The tension would be dependent on the angles of the links, the tension applied on the end of the rope, and the weight being supported by the device. This model was based on the Capstan equation (Equation 1 below), which relates rope tension, rope deflection angle, and coefficients of friction. According to this equation, the greater the angle at which the rope is deflected around a circular drum, the lower the holding tension required to support a given load [1].

$$T_{load} = T_{hold}e^{\mu\psi} \quad (1)$$

where

μ = Coefficient of Friction

ϕ = Deflection Angle

2.2 Assumptions

Some simplifying assumptions were made in modeling the device. We assumed that the ends of the rope were vertical. We also assumed that the links were fixed at their joints, meaning that for a given configuration, the angles will not change when the device is placed on the rope and tension is placed on the rope. In a future analysis it would be interesting to allow the links to pivot, creating variable tension depending on the magnitude of the load applied to the device.

For our analysis we assumed a 400 lb. load hung from the device. The model has a coefficient of friction between the rope and the aluminum of the device to be 0.25, which can be considered average for rope on aluminum.

2.3 Optimization

The objective of our optimization, as mentioned previously, was to minimize tension in the rope. In this case the design variables were the angles for each link. The optimization was subject to a number of constraints. The tension in the top of the rope was constrained to be equal to the tension at the bottom of the rope plus the weight of the person. This ensured that the device would be capable of supporting the required 400 lb. load. An inequality constraint was created to ensure that the links would not double back on each other, as this would be unfeasible in a real device. The link angles were constrained to be between 0 and 180 degrees, and the pretension applied to the bottom of the rope was constrained to be between 1 and 500 lbs.

The optimization was done in Python using SNOPT, a gradient based algorithm from the pyOptSparse package. In order to explore the optimal designs obtained with different numbers of links, we ran the optimizer multiple times while varying the link number between each run. The link number was varied between 3 and 8 links.

As will be further discussed in the Results section, we found that there were a number of optimal solutions for a given number of links, and so we eventually ran the optimizer 20 times for each link number in order to identify all of the local optima. We also generated random link angles as the starting point for each optimization to further help us explore the function space. After doing this, we compared all of the optimal designs for all link numbers to find an overall optimum and explore trends.

3. RESULTS

In Figure 1 is shown the optimal link configuration found using the SNOPT method. The configuration can support 400 lbs with a minimum pretension of 22.7 lbs. The design has 6 links and has the rope zig zag through the link configuration. We found that adding additional links would decrease the pretension needed but it was not significant.

To get to this design we optimized configurations for different numbers of links. A plot of the Pareto front is seen in figure 2. Below are the optimal designs for each set of links along with the minimum initial tension. As can be seen a few trends existed. All optimal designs seems to have the starting link as horizontal. The zig zag pattern is dominant because it offers a larger angle of rope wrapping and it is the default pattern given when rope wrapping. Looking at the Pareto front we find an additional pattern where even links significantly improve the optimal design when compared to adding a single link. One explanation for this phenomenon

Figure 1: This is an example of a given design that the optimizer takes in and modifies

is that an even number of links means an odd number of rods to wrap around. An odd number of rods allow symmetry in the rope wrapping.

For any set number of links there exist multiple designs that have the same optimal pretension. Each optimal design is unique making it difficult to detect a pattern that explains the significant efficiency improvements of adding even links. In Figure 3 examples of the optimal solutions for each number of links is given. The final interesting pattern we found was that optimal designs tended to be fairly open. This may have been because we limited the relative angles on of the links so that they would not double back on themselves, creating an unfeasible solution. It would seem that an optimal design would have the least number of tangent wrapping (not weaving) as possible, but in some cases, such as the 5 link optimization, several tangents still exist in the optimal design.

Figure 2: The number of links versus the optimal pretension required

4. CONCLUSION

Figure 3: One optimal design from each optimization of link numbers 3-6

This optimization gave us some interesting insight into what may be an optimal link configuration for a rappel device. We believe that this algorithm could be helpful in suggesting a starting point for new designs based on certain desired parameters.

We propose that the six link design is most desirable because the minimal improvements gained through adding more links is offset by the increased device size and complexity.

There are a number of items that could be done as future work on this algorithm. The rope angles on the end links could be adjusted to accurately mimic the orientation that the device would be in when tension is applied to the end of the rope. The current vertical end conditions do not account for the fact that an actual device designed as those we have shown would rotate due to the moment created by the rope tension. Another valuable improvement would be varying other parameters such as the radii of the rods and the lengths of the links to see the effect on the optimal solution. Trying gradient-free optimization methods such as a genetic algorithm would also be interesting, as this may reveal more local optima.

Beyond improving the actual optimization, this is admittedly a fairly limited analysis and there are many other factors to consider when designing an optimal rappel device. The model that we have developed here can serve as a basis for a much more extensive analysis and aid those interested in developing more analytical ways of determining rappel device performance.

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